

Supporting Information

A Versatile Luminescent Ga-Organic Framework with Multi-emission Centers as a Blue LED and Fluorescent Probe for Low-temperature Detection and Selective Fe³⁺ Sensing

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1. Materials and Methods.

Reagents: All reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources without further purification. The organic ligand biphenyl-3,4',5-tricarboxylic acid (H_3L , 97%) were purchased from CHEMSOON Co., Ltd (Shanghai, China). $Ga(NO_3)_3 \cdot xH_2O$ (99.9%), $Sc(NO_3)_3 \cdot xH_2O$ (99.99%), DMF (N,N-dimethylformamide, 99.5%) and HAC (acetic acid, 99.5%) were purchased from Aladdin Industrial Inc (Shanghai, China). $NaNO_3$ (AR), KNO_3 (AR), $Cd(NO_3)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (AR), $Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (AR), $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (AR), $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (AR), $Al(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ (AR), $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ (AR), $Ni(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (AR), EtOH (ethanol, AR), $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$ (AR), $BaSO_4$ (AR) and KBr (AR) were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd (Shanghai, China).

Characterization: Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern was collected by a Rigaku MiniFlex600 diffractometer with $Cu K\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$, 40 kV, 15 mA) at room temperature by 0.02° steps. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the range of $4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The UV-vis absorption spectra measured on a Hitachi U-3900 UV/vis spectrophotometer using $BaSO_4$ pellets in the range of $700\text{--}200 \text{ nm}$ at room temperature. The temperature-dependent luminescent measurements were recorded a Horiba FluoroMax+ spectrofluorometer. The solid-state photoluminescence properties and metal ions sensing were recorded on Hitachi F-7100 fluorescence spectrophotometer at room temperature.

Figure S1. FT-IR spectra of the organic ligand and SNNU-63.

Figure S2. Excitation and emission spectra of the free H₃PTC ligand.

Figure S3. Excitation and emission spectra of SNNU-63.

Figure S4. The solid-state UV-Vis absorption spectra of SNNU-63 and the free H₃PTC ligand at room temperature.

Figure S5. The corresponding CIE 1931 chromaticity diagram of SNNU-63 at room temperature.

(a)

(b)

Figure S6. Comparison of photo for SNNU-63 under the natural light (a) and UV 254 nm light (b).

Figure S7. Excitation and emission spectra of SNNU-63 MOF aqueous suspension.

Figure S8. Luminescence intensity ($I_{382\text{ nm}}$) of SNNU-63 to different metal ions in aqueous (0.4 mM) under excitation of 288 nm.

Figure S9. Fluorescence quenching of SNNU-63 dispersed in aqueous solutions of twelve different metal cations (0.4 mM).

Figure S10. Linearity relationship of luminescent intensity of SNNU-63 and Fe^{3+} ion at low concentrations.

Figure S11. The reversibility and recyclability of SNNU-63 based on the maximum emission intensity at 382 nm in water (1 mL 2 mg/mL) in the presence of 2 mL 0.6 mM aqueous solution of Fe^{3+} ions.